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**EFFECT OF REALIA INSTRUCTION ON STUDENTS' ACHIEVEMENT IN FOUR-STROKE-
ENGINE-OPERATION IN TECHNICAL COLLEGES IN NORTH-WEST, NIGERIA**

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Abstract

The study investigated the effect of Realia Instructional Method (RIM) on students' academic achievement in four-stroke-engine-operation in technical colleges in North-West Nigeria. The study was guided by two objectives, two research questions, and two null hypotheses. The study anchored on theory of constructivism and social-constructivist theories of learning. Pretest-posttest experimental design was used for the study. The population consists of 480 technical colleges students in SS1 Motor Vehicle Mechanics Work (MVMW) in 2020/2021 academic session in north-west Nigeria. Two intact classes in two technical colleges consisting of a total of 75 SS1 students (37 experimental group and 38 control group) were randomly selected as sample for the study. Pretest, Posttest achievement test were used as instrument for data collection. The instrument contained 40 multiple choice test items with reliability coefficient of 0.85 obtained using split half method. Data collected was analyzed using mean and standard deviation and t-test was used to test the two null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The result revealed among others that there was a significant difference in the use of realia and conventional method, in favour of the realia instructional method. It is therefore recommended that teachers should be using RIM in teaching four-stroke-engine-operation in technical colleges and MVMW in general. This will encourage teachers to cover all parts of the curriculum. School administrators should encourage the shift from theory based/lecture method of teaching to practical through the use of Realia Instructional Method.

Keywords: Realia Instructional Method, Achievement, Students, Four-Stroke-Engine-Operation

Introduction

The importance of Motor Vehicle Mechanics Work (MVMW) education in National development can never be over emphasized. Through MVMW education, students acquire skills, knowledge and competencies needed for technological advancement and self-reliance in repair, maintenance and services of motor vehicles. Oranu (2014) opined that technology education (MVMW inclusive) is the major key that can unlock the door to development. The main aim of MVMW according to the curriculum of National Board for Technical Education (NABTEB 2013) and national policy on education (National policy on Education, 2013) is to produce competent and skilled craftsmen with good back ground knowledge on repairs, maintenance and services of motor vehicle. In Nigeria, despite the importance of MVMW in national development, research evidences show that there is a general decline on students' academic achievement in the subject. Chief examiners report of 2011 – 2017 indicated that there is decline on students' academic achievement in MVMW. Popper (2017) opined that many

students cannot interpret simple diagnosis in motor vehicle. What could be the cause? According to Ibgeradja (2009), many factors are responsible for the poor academic achievement of students in MVMW examination. These factors, according to the author include: (i) Inability of the teachers to put across the concepts of the lesson to the students, (ii) lack of skills and competencies required for teaching, (iii) shortage of qualified basic technology teachers, (iv)'; inadequate teaching materials, and (v) inappropriate teaching methodology. In the same vein, Harris and Sas (2018) reported that the most important school based determining factor that affects students' achievement is the teacher's quality and methodology. Pensky, (2010) stated that the conventional (lecture) teaching method is not effective because the teaching is basically theoretical. Dewey (1916) stated that if we teach today as we taught yesterday, we rob our children of tomorrow. This could be synthesized to mean that teaching is dynamic and requires dynamic approach different from what it was yesterday. The advancement in technology has created a leverage that allow for teachers to explore in the delivery of lessons, using different teaching methods, such as realia in areas where the real object(s) are not readily available or too abstract to understand by the students.

To promote the learning outcome of students, there is agitation for a shift to the learning theory of Shulman (2016) which emphasized the use of tools that will carry message, stimulate cognitive and feeling that motivates students. Cameron (2010) stated that when the teacher teaches practical to the young learners, the young learners need related objects they can see and touch. Vasquez (2014) stated that choosing appropriate media for distributing message stimulates the mind, feeling, interest and attention of the learners which thus boost the academic achievement of students. Yilmaz (2013) highlighted that there are many kinds of media that help learning process such as realia (real object) for teaching and learning. Lee, Amini, and Latha (2021) reported that the use of realia instructional enabled students to (a) construct their own meaning; (b) current learning is developed on the previous learning; (c) the learner is involved in meaningful social interactions; and (d) the learning is built through the use of authentic involvement with the learning.

Realia instructional method (RIM) is the teaching method, which involves the use of objects from real life used in classroom instruction by educators to improve students 'understanding of real-life situation. Nachimias and Nachimias (2014) defined realia (model) as "a likeness of something and/or representation of reality. In other words, model depicts the actual representation of the original. Realia can be classified into "conceptual and hardware. This study sees realia as the likeness of something or original and representation of reality (real), in this study the researcher is using realia as a hardware teaching method. Yilmaz (2013) also reported that Realia connects learners with the key focal point of a lesson by following the connection between learned material and the object of the lesson. This research intended to determine the effect of realia on the achievement of student in four-stroke-engine-operation in technical colleges in North-West Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Reports of National Board for Technical Education (NBTE 2018/19 session) and National Business and Technical Education Board (NABTEB 2018/19 session) external examiners have shown that the general achievement of students in NABTEB is not encouraging as the students are not achieving to their highest potential. Students of Motor Vehicle Mechanics Work are not exceptional. Also available statistics from technical colleges under study showed that academic achievement of the students at both promotional examination and final NTC II examination is not encouraging (Daramola, Owolabi, & Olutola, 2018). The situation is frustrating and will hamper the career aspirations of students and manpower needs in the area of MVMW. The persistent poor-level achievement of students in MVMW is not unconnected with the way teachers in technical colleges teach through the use of conventional method in which teachers use only text books content to teach with little or no teaching aid or instructional models This is very appalling when there is different medium through which lessons

can be delivered, among others are the use of RIM. lack of keeping abreast with modern pedagogical approaches by teachers and use of the advantage of modern technologies in teaching, the researcher attempted to determine the most effect of RIM.

Purpose of the Study

The aim of the study was to determine the effects of Realia Instruction method (RIM) in Four-stroke-cycle-engine-operation on achievement of students of motor vehicle mechanics work in technical colleges of North-West Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to achieve the following objectives:

1. Determine the difference between the pre-test mean achievement scores of students in experimental group and those in control group in Four-stroke engine operation in Technical Colleges in North-West Nigeria.
2. Determine the difference between the posttest mean achievement scores of students taught Four-stroke-engine-operation using Realia Instructional method (RIM) and those taught using conventional method in Technical Colleges in North-West Nigeria.

Research Questions

This study provided answers to the following research questions

- 1 What is the difference between the pre-test mean academic achievement scores of students in experimental group and those in control group in Four-stroke engine operation in Technical Colleges in North-West Nigeria?
- 2 What is the difference between the posttest mean achievement scores of students taught Four-stroke-engine-operation using RIM and those taught using conventional method in Technical Colleges in North-West Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses guided the study

- H0₁** There is no significant difference between the pre-test mean achievement scores of students in experimental group and those in control group in Four-stroke engine operation in Technical Colleges in North-West Nigeria.
- H0₂** There is no significant difference between the posttest mean achievement scores of students taught Four-stroke-engine-operation using RIM and those taught using conventional method in Technical Colleges in North-West Nigeria

Literature Review

Instructional materials are materials that help in deepening students' understanding. Afdal, Disman and Munir (2016) conceptualized instructional material as aids which make it easier for the teacher to impart knowledge and skills to the learners. Concurring with Afdal et al (2016). Availability of instructional materials and facilities save time, make learning more effective and promote interest for both teacher and the learners. Ricardo (2018) viewed instructional materials as tools used to supplement the written or spoken word in the transmission of knowledge, attitude or idea, and to emphasize, clarify or vitalize the instruction. Silver (2010) asserted that teaching aids or instructional materials consist of carefully planned and selected resources to facilitate teaching and learning process, instructional materials are all the object, things, people used to promote the teaching and learning of different subjects/courses, which include MVMW. The organized, combination and utilization of materials, equipment and people facilitate the presentation of content for the realization of the stated objectives.

John (2015) described instructional materials as any devices, pieces of equipment graphic representation and illustration designed and used to assist the learners to learn comprehensively.

Okpe (2018) explained further that. instructional materials are anything that can be used by the teacher and learners before ,during and after the lesson to ease the achievement of the objectives, in other words, instructional materials are tools that facilitate the transmission, understanding of knowledge and appreciation of concepts, skills, values and attitudes, the use of such materials task the various sense organs of the learners, encouraging their active participation in the instructional process, learners are opportune to contribute in the instructional process through their various senses, their understanding is promoted and teacher delivered from making lengthy explanation that can further confused the students. Okoye and Olu (2016) opined that, instructional materials are all the tools that can be used by the teacher to help and provide encouragement to learners and learning activities. This kind of material brings together learners and materials in systematic co-operation to effectively solve educational problems. In another word these instructional materials are called “realia”.

Sanjel (2014) viewed realia like text books, chalk board, models, comics chart, and other non-projected tools which brings about efficacy and efficiency in the teaching and learning process and in variably, promotes and enhance the achievement of instructional objectives. Sanjel (2014) stated that, in order to meet the objective of his lesson, the teacher must employ various types of aids and appeal to different senses. In psychology of using instructional materials is suffice to saying that “what I hear I forget and what I see, I remember, but what I do, I understand”. Brown (2013) said teachers like other medical doctors and professional workers, needed essential tools and equipment to do their best work, it is undeniable that, the century figure in any learning situation is always the student. From the above it can be synthesized to mean that any physical object that is presented or displayed for students to see, touch and/or use to enhance their learning process is called “Realia.” These are items that are mostly used and discarded by owners.

Studies have revealed that realia may be acquired by schools through the following means: i, Collecting Items from the Immediate Locality based on the advice of the teacher, ii, learners could collect these items from their neighbouring motor mechanics workshops like used brake pads/shoes master brake cylinder, burnt valves and worn out piston, connecting rod and other engine parts Teachers and learners can produce some cheap models and material like charts, as realia. Governmental and non-governmental organization occasionally, acquires and distributes to schools some tools equipment models and even more sophisticated instructional materials and equipment such as physical instructional aids, projectors and other laboratory, equipment. Non- governmental organizations such as UNESCO, UNDP, UNICEF, DFID, USAID, ICA also donate instructional materials to schools (Obeka, 2010). Education resources center (ERC) is another place where varieties of instructional materials are produced/exist for use by teachers, learners and other interested individuals within a school or an area. consequently E.R.C can be created by schools for the development and production of some of these instructional aids.

Methodology

The study adopted pretest posttest quasi experimental design. Specifically, a pre-test post-test control group design. Bhardwaj, (2019), opined that when study involves estimating the causal effect of treatment on target population without random assignment, quasi experimental design should be used.

Table 1: Diagrammatic presentation of the Research Design

Group	Pre-test	Treatment	Post-test
Experiment Group (E)	X_{11}	Realia 0	X_{12}
Control Group (C)	X_{21}	Conventional	X_{22}

Source: Bhardwaj (2019).

Where:

$X_{_}$ represents observations

0 represents treatment

This research work was carried out in North-west, Nigeria The population for the study was the entire 480 National Technical Certificate (NTC I) students in 2020/2021 academic session in all the 15 accredited Government Science Technical Colleges offering MVMW in North-West Nigeria. The sample and sampling technique for this study was simple random sampling technique where two intact classes were randomly selected for the study. According to Bhardwaj (2019), sample is a small portion of the population from which information may be collected and analyzed for the purpose of describing or making conclusion or inferences on the total population. Random sampling refers to the unpredictability of an event or individual, though the events can be predicted successfully in aggregate (John and Benedict 2015). The first school selected was assigned to experimental group, and the second school was assigned to control group.

Two instruments were used for data collection. The first was Pretest-Four-Stroke-Engine-Operation Achievement test (PFSOA₁), and the second instrument was posttest Four-Stroke-Engine-Operation Achievement test (PFSOA₂). Each of the instruments contained 40 multiple choice questions with A to D options. The PFSOA₁ otherwise known as pre-test was used to determine the academic position of the students before the treatment. The PFSOA₁ was reshuffled and was called PFSOA₂ which was used to determine the academic attainment of the students after treatment, The instrument was adopted from 2012-2017 past examination question papers of National Business and Technical Education Board (NABTEB), West Africa Examination Council (WAEC) and National Examination council (NECO). This was so because all the three examination bodies conduct Technical Certificate Examination for students of Technical Colleges in Nigeria.

Two experts from Automobile Technology Education Unit of Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Bauchi and Modibbo Adama University Yola validated the instrument. The experts scrutinized the instruments by checking the contents and the appropriateness of the items.

The reliability of the “Four-Stroke-cycle Engine-Operation Achievement Test” (FSOAT) was established by testing the internal consistency of the test items using Split-Half method. A reliability coefficient of .855 was obtained. Difficulty index of 0.80 was also obtained while discrimination index had a highest score of 0.87 and the lowest score of 0.77. The average discriminating index was 0.84. All the items were considered satisfactory for the study and therefore retained. Two trained Research Assistants were involved in the study. Individualistic training was organized, to attend to their individual needs since each of the research assistant used specific teaching method.

The teaching lasted for a period of four weeks. At the end of the exercise, the post-test achievement test was administered. The whole exercises lasted for five weeks. The data collected was analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) to answer the research questions while t-test was used in testing the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Table 2: Research Question Decision Rule

S/No	Mean difference	Decision
1.	±0.1 to ±4.99	Slight difference (SD)
2.	±5.00 to ±9.99	Moderate difference (MD)
3.	±10.00 to ±14.99	Large difference (LD)
4.	±15 and above	Very large difference (VLD)

Source: Olatoye and Adekoya (2010)

Results and Discussion

Results of Research Questions

The results of research questions were as presented in Tables 3 to 6

Research question one

What is the difference between the pre-test mean academic achievement of students in experimental group and those in control group in Four-stroke engine operation in Technical Colleges in North-West Nigeria?

The descriptive statistics used to answer research question one presented in Table 3 revealed the mean score of 19.74 with standard deviation of 9.25 for students in control group. Students in Experimental Group had mean of 19.70 with standard deviation of 9.15. The mean difference obtained from the two groups of students was ± 0.04. The obtained mean difference was slight according to research question decision rule on table 2 hence, the difference was considered not significant.

Table 3: The Pre-test Mean Academic Achievement

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean difference
Control	38	19.74	9.25	± 0.04
Experimental	37	19.70	9.15	

Research question two

What is the difference between posttest mean achievement score of students taught Four-stroke-engine-operation using RIM (experimental group) and those taught using conventional method in Technical Colleges in North-West Nigeria?

The descriptive result of research question two presented in Table 4 revealed the post-test mean score of 20.13 with standard deviation of 8.58 for students in control. Students in the experimental group had mean of 61.43 with standard deviation of 14.54. The mean score of students in Experimental Group was found to be higher with 28.28. The result therefore indicated that there was large difference. The result was in favour of student taught Four-stroke-engine-operation using Realia Instructional method.

Table 4: The Realia Posttest Mean Academic Achievements

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference
Control	38	20.13	8.58	±41.3
Experimental	37	61.43	14.54	

Null Hypotheses

The results of tested null hypotheses were as presented in Tables 5 to 6

Null hypothesis one

There is no significant difference among the pre-test mean achievement scores of students in experimental group and those in control group in Four-stroke engine operation in Technical Colleges in North-West Nigeria?

The analysis of Independent Sample t-test of null hypothesis one in Table 5 revealed that the *p-value* was 0.987. The *p-value* obtained was greater than alpha value ($0.987 > 0.05$), the result therefore indicated that there was no significant difference among the pretest mean achievement scores of the two groups of students involved in the study. The hypothesis was therefore retained.

Table5: The result of Independent Sample t-test

Group	N	Mean	SD	Df	Sig	T	Sig(2 tailed)
Control	38	19.74	9.25	73	0.832	.016	0.987
Experimental	37	19.70	19.15				

Null hypothesis two

There is no significant difference between posttest mean achievement scores of students taught Four-stroke-engine-operation using RIM and those taught using conventional method in Technical Colleges in North-West Nigeria?

The result of Independent Sample t-test presented in Table 6 revealed that, the mean value of 20.13 with standard deviation of 8.58 for students in control group. Students in the Experimental Group I had mean of 61.43 with the standard deviation of 14.54 at degree of freedom of 73. The *t-value* obtained was -15.026 and the $p=.000$. The *p-value* obtained was less than the alpha value of 0.05. The result suggested that there was significant difference between posttest mean achievement score of the students, in favour of students in experimental group. The hypothesis was therefore rejected.

Table 6: Independent Sample t-test for posttest

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	Sig.	T	Sig. (2-tailed)
Control	38	20.13	8.58	73	.006	-15.026	.000
Experimental	37	61.43	14.54				

Findings of the Study

1. The finding of research question one and test of corresponding null hypothesis showed there was no significant difference among the pre-test mean academic achievement of students in experimental group and those in control group in Four-stroke engine operation in Technical Colleges in North-West Nigeria.
2. The result of research question two and test of corresponding null hypothesis two suggested that there was significant difference between posttest mean achievement score of students taught Four-stroke-engine-operation using Realia Instructional Method (RIM) and those taught using Conventional Method in Technical Colleges in North-West Nigeria, meaning that the use of realia was very effective.

Discussion of Finding

This study investigated the effect of realia and computer aided instructional methods in teaching four stroke cycle engine operation on the achievement of students in motor vehicle mechanics work against those students taught four stroke cycle engine operation using conventional method in motor vehicle mechanics work at technical colleges in North-West Nigeria. The result of research question one disclosed that there was no difference between the pre-test mean scores of the

two groups of students involved in the study. The test of null hypothesis one, disclosed that the difference was not significant. The pretest was conducted to determine the entry level of the students in order to avoid any biasness. The study, further buttressed the claim of Obeka (2010) on the use of pretest to determine the students entry level in the conduct of the research work. The result of research question two showed that there was difference between the post-test mean achievement scores of students taught Four-stroke-engine-operation using Realia instructional method (RIM) and those taught using conventional method. The test of null hypothesis two further affirmed that the difference was significance.

Conclusion

The outcome of the study shows that if teachers were adopting the right instructional methods like RIM, the poor achievement of students in four-stroke-engine-operation of students in technical colleges will be enhanced in North Western Nigeria. The study indicated that the use of RIM has the potential of enhancing the understanding of four-stroke-engine-operation and concept of MVMW trade and general classroom participation of students thereby improve their achievement, by adoption of RIM, will in no small measure improve the academic achievement of MVMW students in technical college in North western Nigeria this is envisaged to be of immense help to the teachers and the students alike, in the delivery and understanding the complete concept of MVMW and general lessons that may be taught using the RIM pedagogical approach.

Recommendations

In this study it was found to be more initiative by looking inward by try to make sure that no part or aspect of the curriculum is left out or skipped in the course of teaching four-stroke engine-operation and MVMW in general therefore it is recommended that:

- i. Teachers of MVMW should revisit the issue of instructional method used in classroom/workshop with a view to make a revolutionary change to include the use of RIM to enhance the teaching of four-stroke-engine operation to improve the academic achievement of students in technical colleges in North western Nigeria
- ii. Teachers of MVM and the students should be seriously encouraged to shift from theory based/lecture method by providing all necessary support to actualize the practice and use of RIM in the absence of the original instructional material for four-stroke-engine-operation. Teachers of MVM should learn to look inward in the absence of any practical material, part/component or vehicle with a view to adopt the RIM instead of suspending or skip the topic or lesson in four-stroke-engine-operation.

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